

A Historical Overview of Women Medical Facilities in Jaipur Princely State (1900–1940)

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Abstract

This paper presents a historical analysis of women's medical facilities in the Jaipur Princely State from 1900 to 1940, focusing on the intersection of colonial influence, indigenous factors, and socio-cultural transformation. It explores the evolution of healthcare infrastructure, focusing on the establishment of women-centric institutions such as Mayo Hospital, Zenana Hospital, and Lady Willingdon Hospital. The study highlights the challenges brought forward by patriarchal traditions like purdah and the lack of female medical staff to access of such facilities to women. It also examines the role of missionaries, native reformers, and Jaipur rulers in advancing women's health. By using archival records, administrative reports, and contemporary accounts, the paper argues that despite resistance, modern medical reforms gradually improved women's healthcare access and professional participation.

Keywords Women's Health in Colonial India, Zenana, Jaipur Princely State, Colonial Medical Policy, Gender and Medicine

Introduction

Indians have been aware of the importance of medical facilities since ancient times. However, the institutionalization of medical facilities in India was brought by the European powers. The recent historiography is advancing beyond the conventional views by highlighting the endeavours undertaken by Europeans, particularly in the areas of medical reforms and the promotion of healthcare which transformed Indian society. Scholars differ in their opinions, with some considering these reforms as part of a broader strategy of imperialism[1], while others highlight their positive aspects, especially in the areas under close control of the British.

Being a confederate, Rajputana unquestionably benefited from these healthcare reforms implemented by the British. The colonial era in Rajasthan was marked by drastic transformations in cultures, ideologies, and socio-religious aspects. Various scholars assert the modernity which pervaded Jaipur's princely state with the coming of the British Raj. This resulted in a significant contribution to the medical and healthcare development of the women of Jaipur. The process of medical reformation in Jaipur was marked by the combined efforts of the natives and the British institutions. Keeping in mind the social history of Rajasthan in the early and medieval times, the land was patriarchal and women lived without any contact with the outside world, and in such a situation, these social actions became the catalyst for change and brought medical reforms to the Rajput households.

Recent scholarship has attempted to explore the individuality of women in the light of medical history. Pioneering efforts in the field of female healthcare were made by European missionary women like Fanny Butler and Clara Swain, where the latter was closely related to the Khatri region of Rajasthan.[2]

Objective of study

This research paper attempts to explore a generalised study of healthcare initiatives for women of Jaipur Princely state during the years 1900 to 1940. The paper traces the roles and initiatives of natives and British institutions in reforming healthcare for the women of Jaipur, advocating for improved healthcare and ensuring access to such facilities. The study probes to identify the reception of these reforms by women and explore the tension between cultural traditions and modernity. It delves into the responses of women to this exposure and the reaction of patriarchy towards this female-centric healthcare revolution during the period under study.

The research employs detailed study of primarily sources including primary sources like Jaipur Agency Documents and Jaipur Confidential Reports from Rajasthan State Archival Department. The paper makes extensive use of Reports on Administration of Jaipur State, Rajasthan District Gazetteers, Annual Report of The National Association for Supplying Female Medical Aid by Women in India, AIWC Report available for the period under study.

Review of Literature

Hendley (1900) provides details about evolution of healthcare infrastructure, medical practices, and policy frameworks in colonial India and their effects on the healthcare for women. He gives a compilation of relevant statistical data from various administrative reports, and detailed accounts of indigenous healthcare system in Rajputana.

Forbes (2005) gives a detailed analysis of the healthcare apparatus for native women during the colonial period in India. She explores the role and initiatives of the British in the introduction of healthcare in Colonial India, the institution of midwifery, and its eventual 'salvation' by the British and traces the struggles and achievements of native 'Lady Doctors' and other female medical practitioners like nurses and midwives.[3]

Mukharjee (2005) proposes a similar view that gender and healthcare were linked to the 'civilizing' agenda of the British and household became a 'scientific' topic. Sehrawat too expresses her views on 'maternal imperialism' and its effect on the development of healthcare for native women of India.

Burton (2007) explores the ideological aspects of imperial feminism and 'Oriental womanhood.' She examines how British feminists positioned themselves as European 'sisters' and native women as 'white woman's burden'.

Taknet (2016) provides a thorough history of Jaipur, concentrating on the city's medical and cultural heritage. He even discusses Begum Sali Muttaba, Jaipur's first female physician.

Tanwar (2017) in her book "Gulabi Nagri Ka Aarthik Avam Sanskritik Itihas" dedicates an entire chapter to the medical facilities of Jaipur Princely State.

Pathak (2024) in her research paper "Jaipur Lunatic Asylum: Navigating Institutional History amid Colonial Rule (1895-1940s)" gives clear detail of the condition of female mental patients in Jaipur Princely State.

Main Text

The Medical Apparatus

Ever since its inception, Jaipur has been known for its modernity mostly due to the reformatory actions of its founder, Maharaja Sawai Jai Singh II. This reformation was confined to the use of modern science and technology in the creation of architectural marvels of Jaipur city. The strongest wave of revolution hit the city with the accession of Maharaja Sawai Ram Singh II who made several attempts to culture Jaipur into a progressive state.[4] His modernisation was carried forward by his successor Maharaja Sawai Madho Singh II, who contributed large sum of money to the medical facilities and funds throughout the country. Prior to the rise of Western medical facilities in Jaipur, the sick was treated by indigenous practitioners like Baid (Hindu physicians), Jaitis (Jain priests), Hakims (Muslim physicians), Jarrah (barber-surgeons), Satyas (couchers), pansaris (druggists), bairagis and fakirs. The obstetrics and gynaecology were majorly overseen by dhais or midwives.

Although the agency in Jaipur was established on the 18th of March 1821, the first allopathic dispensary was not opened until 1844. The presence of a Residency Hospital, two miles away from the city, ensured the availability of medical assistance since 1821. The contemporary social construct was visible in the reaction of citizen towards the

modernization of medical facilities, as in the year 1869, the attendance ratio of women was just 20.79% in comparison to men.[5] This difference was prevalent due to various factors. The rigid use of the purdah system among the women of Rajputana marked their confinement to households and limited their interaction with the outer world. This resulted in a lack of awareness which along with the shackles of patriarchy, minimised the attendance of women at hospitals. This difference was equally deepened by the lack of female doctors and women staff at hospitals, which was another reason why women avoided going to the hospitals.

The inception of Mayo Hospital in 1870 was the milestone in the modern medical facilities in Jaipur.[6] It became functional in 1875. The breakthrough in the field of women healthcare came with the establishment of a female wing in the hospital which was headed by a Lady doctor and supported by female staff. The presence of female staff resulted in positive reception of modern facilities.[7] By the year 1915, the association of women patients with the Mayo Hospital increased and 46.53% of patients were women and children, in comparison to in 1908, when 41.79% of patients were women and children.[8] This increase in the ratio of women and child patients in the time period of just 7 years, depicted the positive reception of hospital facilities by the women of Jaipur. Yet, the intermixing of 'respectable' women with 'other' women in the Zenana hospitals was a pressing reason why the former avoided hospitals. This led to increased concern for the social division of medical facilities after 1915. This resulted in the establishment of a separate Zenana ward called the Lady Hardinge ward, for the 'patients of better class.' It consisted of 'nine complete suits of rooms, each with an upper story for the separate accommodation of Purdah patients.'[9]

Establishment of the Zenana Hospital was a result of positive reception of modern medical facilities by the women of Jaipur and the hospital was considered as the most significant step taken in the field of modernised healthcare for women in Jaipur princely state. The aim of the hospital was to 'render medical aid to women of all classes'.[10] The hospital was supervised and supported by all female staff. The Lady doctor who headed the hospital, was housed in a bungalow near the site of the hospital. The construction of the hospital began in 1928-29 and it became functional on 13th April 1931 when the building was unveiled by the Maharani Sahiba of Jaipur. An excerpt from the opening speech of Her Highness depicts the entire working of the Zenana Hospital.

The hospital was initially administered by the Scottish Mission at Jaipur and was later transferred to the Director of Medical Services on 13th April 1933. The presence of privacy due to all female staff and lady doctors invited women to the hospital. The overall reception of the hospital among the women of Jaipur was immensely positive.[11]

The foundation for a new hospital was laid by His Highness Maharaja Man Singh II in 1934 on the lines of the Mayo Hospital to decrease the overcrowding in the former. This hospital came to be known as the Lady Willingdon Hospital, became functional on 15th October 1942.[12] This hospital was equipped with the latest technology and was designed to accommodate 120 patients. The grants for this hospital were given by Tazimi Sardars and other leading merchants of the times.[13] In the same year as the foundation of the Lady Willingdon Hospital, the plan for another hospital was passed as well. It was inaugurated on 11th March 1936 and became the celebrated Sawai Man Singh Hospital, after its founder His Highness Maharaja Man Singh II.

Mental Hospitals

According to the Census of 1891, there were 384 individuals classified as lunatics in Jaipur and 123 of them were females.[14] Hendley summarises various factors that contributed to the rise of insanity among women. These conditions include puerperal mania, delusional insanity, perversion and epileptic fits, primarily triggered by the loss of possessions or relationships, particularly children.[15] With reference to the cultural scenario of Rajasthan, a dakan is a living women who affects people with evil eye. Such women according to oral histories, 'consumes children's livers (kaleja)' and should be killed.[16]

Notably, the characteristics of mental illness in women, such as abnormal sexual behaviour and mania can be connected parallelly to the myth of witches or practitioners of black magic, who are said to have physical relations with young men, exhibit manic behaviour and look like a vampire. Interestingly, Hendley quotes the loss of a child or relative as a potential factor contributing to the mental instability of women, which is equivalent to the belief that a woman who was treated badly by her family or who died during childbirth comes back as daayan, dakan, bhootni or churail.[17] Traditional beliefs attributed mental illness as a result of possession by evil spirits. This stigmatized psychiatric care and supported religious or folk treatments, often involving local witch

doctors such as ojhas, tantriks or bhagats, rather than seeking scientific medical therapy. Similarly, temples take place of hospitals for such women.

The first lunatic asylum in Jaipur was established in 1881 under the Jail department. Lunatics were 'incarcerated inside cells.' [18] This depicts that the care for mental patients in this period was confined to rudimentary forms like sedation, isolation, and restraint and focused on containment rather than comprehensive treatment, which was changed in 1922, when the Lunatic asylum was shifted near Chandpole Gate and part-time doctors were appointed to provide medical supervision to the lunatics. The process of institutionalization of medical facilities for mental patients was completed when the Mental Hospital Jaipur started working as an independent body under the under Medical Department of Jaipur State in 1944. In 1908, the number of female lunatics was 21 [19], which decreased to 13 in 1915. [20] The causes for this decline were numerous. The fear of social ostracism can be seen as an important factor. However, in India, a nation deeply rooted in religious and supernatural beliefs, superstitions and folk beliefs had a significant influence on healthcare procedures. This belief, combined with ignorance towards education, led to the inclination towards temples and local witch doctors for the mitigation of mental problems rather than approaching asylums for treatment. This trend is visible with the rise and peak of Balaji Temple at Mehandipur between the years 1899 and 1979. The temple was renowned for dealing with witches, psychiatry and mental health problems. [21] The connection between the two can be established. It is plausible that the decline in insanity cases might be attributed, at least in part, to the practice of transferring such cases to temples instead of asylums.

Reception and Response

Colonial historiography postulated that the social initiatives taken by the British had a liberating effect on the native citizens. Antoinette Burton proposes that it was the European 'sisters' who led to the salvation of Indian women and served them with healthcare, modernity, education and development. [22] A similar view is held by Flavia Agnes, who theorizes that the Indian household became a point of contention between nationalist leaders and colonialists. Agnes states further that it was the 'British Feminists' who came to safeguard the Indian women and secure their rights. [23] Due to significant cultural differences, these historians failed to understand the basic contradiction, the purdah system, which governed the lives of women throughout India. The pre-occupation with purdah was such, that a woman chose to close the door and die in great agony, rather than take medical care by male hands. [24] Purdah pratha was a major factor which limited the reception of medical facilities to its fullest by the women of Jaipur. The medical practitioners associated with the women were mostly dais or midwives, who looked after gynaecology and obstetrics. These traditional Indian birth attendants were seen with disgust by the Europeans. They 'cannot read or write,' 'belonged to the lowest classes,' and were 'most skilled as abortionists'. [25]

Dr. Miss Jerbanoo E. Mistry explains the common perception of dais as: 'The dai considers herself qualified to attend all labours normal and abnormal, and all the pelvic diseases. Cleanliness is a thing unknown to her. Soap and water are her great enemies. Often she is so dirty she stinks, and her hands and nails are covered with dirt, particularly the nails which are long and perfectly black on account of dirt underneath. To ask her to wash her hands before making an examination is to inflict on her a great unforgivable indignity.' [26]

Dais served as the birth attendants for Indian women since ancient times, thus removing the institutions of dais completely was not a practical solution. British thus resorted to transforming the institution of midwifery through training and education. [27] It was expected that training would lead to a decrease in ignorance on the part of the dais. However, despite the positive increase in the number of women opting for modernised healthcare, the ratio of native women pursuing employment in modern health care facilities was grossly limited. The pioneer institution to provide organised training to nurses, nurse-dais and midwives in Jaipur was the State Zenana Hospital. As the engagement of candidates to the profile of nurses and nurse-dais was limited, there was a gross shortage of nurses even in the premier hospitals of Jaipur. [28] The reasons for this indifference were the lack of facilities and the despicable condition of life for nursing services. The income parity, absence of institutionalised education for nursing and midwifery [29] and lack of accommodation facilities resulted in detachment from the profession. [30] Interestingly, the role of dais and female doctors was not confined to providing healthcare. They also served as a link between common women and the government. One such instance is of dais and female doctors being employed as identification of the female pensioners. [31]

Victoria Memorial Fund was a critical initiative targeting the institutionalisation of the dhais in India. The Mayo hospital housed '13 dhais belonging to the families of hereditary midwives'[32] for training under the initiative. The enrolled young women were also given a stipend of 'R 2 mensem' to increase engagement.

The first hospital to provide medical facilities for women of Jaipur was the Mayo Hospital, but it was the foundation of the Lady Hardinge ward as a totally separate ward for women of 'affluent classes', which brought pardah-nashin women to the hospital. The real impetus for female healthcare in Jaipur came with the establishment of the Zenana Hospital in 1931. The hospital was 'designed especially for women,' 'staffed entirely by women,' and was equipped with the latest facilities and technologies. The absence of males and exclusive female surroundings gave women a comfortable environment. It can be seen as an idea of an extended household, where women are serving women and confinements of purdah can be relaxed.

Interestingly, the female doctors were not just mute spectators of the situations which came to fore. An important instance is of Dr. Prem Payari[33], who actively persuaded a military officer out of the hospital as he was misbehaving with the other doctors.

Even after over 50 years since its inception, the turnout of female patients in Mayo Hospital was limited. From 1926 to 1937, the number of beds for females in the Mayo Hospital was confined to 50[34]. Unlike Mayo Hospital, where a single ward was secured for women and the rest of the hospital was accessible to men, Zenana Hospital provided women with comfortable treatment due to its all-women surroundings.

There are numerous instances of the support of royalty and court for the expansion of healthcare for women of Jaipur. Her Highness the Maharani Sahiba of Jaipur, for instance, unveiled the Zenana Hospital and highlighted the importance of medical facilities for women. Notably, the sources of Royal women using these medical facilities and hospitals are unavailable

Conclusion

The paper delves into the generalised history of medical facilities in Jaipur princely states with specific focus on healthcare services for women during the period from 1920 to 1940. The study explores in detail the pioneering initiatives taken in the field of modern medical facilities in Jaipur and how it conflicted with social norms, religious beliefs and patriarchy, which governed the lives of Indian. The role of royalty of Jaipur, especially Maharaja Sawai Ram Singh II, HH Maharaja Sawai Sir Madho Singh II and HH Maharaja Sir Sawai Man Singh II and even the queens of Jaipur, are significant in the domain of development of medical apparatus in Jaipur.

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